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Language, Identity, and Integration in Icelandic Society

Limited Icelandic language proficiency shapes how international students and foreign residents experience belonging and social integration in Iceland.

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By Niccolo Roman

Iceland is often described as a highly English-accessible country, especially within universities, public services, and urban environments. During my time in Iceland, I observed that English was commonly used as a shared language among people from different nationalities. In conversations with individuals from China, Taiwan, the Netherlands, Argentina, Italy, and Spain, English often allowed communication to happen smoothly despite different cultural and linguistic backgrounds.

This experience led me to explore my research question: *“To what extent does limited Icelandic language proficiency affect international students’ and foreign residents’ sense of belonging and social integration in Iceland?”*

This particular research combines academic findings, field observations, and informal conversations to understand how language shapes belonging and social integration in real-life contexts.

For many international students and foreign residents, it is possible to navigate daily life without speaking Icelandic fluently. However, accessibility through English does not fully eliminate the role of language in shaping identity, cultural participation, and a sense of belonging.

Language as Access in Everyday Life

In Iceland, English is commonly used in education, tourism, and public communication, particularly in international university environments. This allows international students and foreign residents to access academic spaces and essential services without requiring complete Icelandic proficiency (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. A multilingual public safety sign at Reynisfjara beach in Iceland, demonstrating the structural use of Icelandic, English, and Mandarin Chinese to communicate with tourists and residents.

During my visit to the University of Iceland, I participated in a discussion and research session with Student Council members. The discussion showed how English plays an important role in communication between local students and international visitors. I learned that international students are present at the university, and because English proficiency is required for admission to many programs, English becomes a key language for academic participation.

While the discussion with Student Council members, I observed that language barriers can still appear even among highly proficient English speakers. For example, Katla occasionally paused to use an Icelandic word or

phrase when explaining certain ideas before finding the closest English equivalent. This suggested that some cultural concepts, expressions, and social meanings may be easier to communicate through Icelandic than through English alone. Sociolinguistic research similarly suggests that Icelandic remains strongly connected to national identity and cultural cohesion, even within an increasingly global environment (Albury).

This highlights that English supports access to education and communication, but Icelandic still carries cultural meaning that influences deeper participation in society.

Social Interaction and Community Integration

Social integration involves more than understanding information. It also includes friendships, participation in communities, and everyday social interaction.

My research used academic articles, field observations, reflective journaling, and informal conversations. A challenge in this research was gaining access to international students and long-term foreign residents, who were my main focus. Because of this limitation, some conversations included tourists and short-term visitors as contextual perspectives rather than the central focus of analysis. These conversations were used to support observations about communication, language use, and social interaction, while academic research remained the primary source of evidence for understanding international students and foreign residents in Iceland.

This limitation influenced how findings were interpreted, as perspectives came from a mix of short-term and indirect experiences rather than only long-term foreign residents. These conversations were not used as primary evidence of immigrant integration in Iceland, but as supporting material to

better understand how language functions in real intercultural communication contexts.

As a scholar experiencing Iceland as a short-term visitor, I also recognize that my own perspective and reliance on English shaped the interactions I had and the aspects of Icelandic society that I was able to observe. Therefore, my findings represent one interpretation of how language influences belonging and integration rather than a complete representation of every international student and foreign resident's experience in Iceland.

Although some of the conversations included tourists and individuals whose experiences occurred outside Iceland, these perspectives remained valuable because they highlighted broader patterns of language adaptation, cultural learning, and social connection. Rather than serving as direct evidence of immigrant integration in Iceland, they provided comparative insights that helped contextualize findings from academic research and observations collected within Icelandic settings.

During my time in Iceland, I had an informal conversation with Le Duyen Huong, who shared her personal experience of moving from Vietnam to France. Although her experience did not take place in Iceland, it provided a perspective on adapting to a new society through language learning and cultural immersion. She explained that learning the local language was important for communication, understanding the environment, and building connections with others. She also highlighted the challenges of adjusting to a new country, including being away from family and adapting to unfamiliar social and cultural expectations (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Le Duyen Huong, originally from Vietnam and now residing in France with her son, discusses her journey of language learning and cultural immersion.

This supports the idea that language learning is closely tied to social integration and forming meaningful connections in a new environment.

I also had a conversation with Sheng Jia (贾胜), who offered a personal perspective on the role of language in social integration. Although he was not speaking from the experience of being a foreign resident in Iceland, Mr. Jia shared that language can absolutely support integration into society. He recognized that English functions as an international language and can facilitate communication between people from different cultural backgrounds. However, he also emphasized that learning the language spoken in the country where someone lives may contribute to a stronger sense of inclusion and a deeper connection with local communities (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Sheng Jia (贾胜), a tourist visiting Iceland from China, sharing his personal perspective on how learning a local language fosters social inclusion and community connection.

This highlights that English enables communication, while Icelandic supports deeper belonging and social integration.

These perspectives reflect the complexity of language and belonging. While English can create accessibility and allow people from different backgrounds to communicate, learning the local language may provide additional opportunities for cultural understanding and deeper social integration. This connects with previous research suggesting that language skills can influence quality of life, trust in institutions, and experiences of belonging among immigrants in Iceland (Hoffman et al.).

Figure 4. A comparison of tourists from the Netherlands (left) and Taiwan (right) in Iceland. Even as short-term visitors, their experiences suggest that while English helps facilitate communication, learning the local language may support deeper cultural understanding and long-term belonging.

Language and Cultural Participation

Language is not only about communication; it also connects to culture and everyday experiences. During my attendance at the performance “*How to Become Icelandic in 60 Minutes*” at Harpa Concert Hall, I observed how humor and storytelling were used to communicate Icelandic identity, traditions, and social expectations; the performance introduced ideas such as the phrase “*Þetta reddast,*” which reflects a cultural attitude that things will work out. It demonstrated that understanding a society involves not only translating words but also understanding the cultural meanings behind them (See Figure 5).

Figure 5. A promotional graphic for the comedy performance “How to Become Icelandic in 60 Minutes” at Harpa Concert Hall, highlighting the intersection of humor, cultural identity, and language learning.

This reinforces that cultural integration involves not only language ability, but also understanding social norms and shared meanings.

While English provides accessibility in many academic and urban spaces, participation in cultural settings may require a deeper understanding of Icelandic language and social norms.

Identity and Belonging in Multilingual Contexts

My research showed that belonging is complex and cannot be explained only by whether a person speaks Icelandic. Many international students and foreign residents can successfully study, work, and communicate using English. However, research suggests that learning Icelandic can support stronger connections with local communities and the Icelandic-speaking society (Skaptadóttir and Innes).

At the same time, experiences of belonging vary based on personal relationships, opportunities for interaction, individual goals, and social environments.

Research on internationalization in Icelandic higher education also shows that English has become increasingly important in university settings, particularly in programs involving international students (Halldórsdóttir and Gollifer). Therefore, English and Icelandic serve different but equally important roles in Icelandic society.

Overall, these findings suggest that Icelandic and English do not replace each other, but operate together in shaping access, identity, and belonging.

Final Reflection: More Than Just Words

After combining academic research with my observations and conversations in Iceland, I found that language operates as more than a tool for communication. It influences access to relationships, cultural participation, and the feeling of being included in a community.

English plays an important role in allowing international students and foreign residents to participate in everyday life in Icelandic society, especially in education and daily interactions. However, Icelandic remains

meaningful for understanding cultural identity and building deeper social connections over time.

My research does not suggest that a person must become fully fluent in Icelandic to belong. Instead, it shows that belonging exists on different levels, where English provides accessibility while Icelandic may create additional opportunities for cultural connection.

From my observations in Iceland, informal conversations with tourists and local residents, more in-depth conversations with Le Duyen Huong and Sheng Jia (贾胜), and academic research findings, I found that belonging in Iceland is shaped by language ability, social interaction, and cultural understanding, where English enables accessibility and participation in daily life, while Icelandic supports deeper social integration and cultural belonging.

Móðurmálið brúar bil og opnar hjörtu; íslensk tunga vísar veginn til samfélagslegrar aðlögunar og dýpri tilheyrslu í hversdagslífinu á Íslandi.
(Icelandic language proficiency affects social integration and the sense of belonging in daily life in Iceland.)

学会在地语言，不仅仅是学会说话，更是打开彼此心房、真正融入这片土地的开始。在多语言的日常交流中，语言能力将深深牵动着人们的社会融入与归属感体验。

(In multilingual daily communication, language ability influences people's experience of social integration and belonging.)

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